

Effective decomposition rate of epoxy resin using a modified shrinking-core model: Enhanced hydrolysis reaction by optimized solvent ratio

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ABSTRACT

Due to their cross-linked structure and stable polymer framework, epoxy resins are difficult to degrade or remelt, leading to significant environmental issues. In this study, the effective degradation rate of cured epoxy resin was investigated using hydrolysis and glycolysis reactions. Before degradation, the ratio of hydrolysis and glycolysis solvents, in which phase separation does not occur, was studied. Various solvent ratios were applied to the cured epoxy resin, and the degradation amount and rate were observed. Based on the experimental results, the effective decomposition rate of epoxy resin was determined using a modified shrinking-core model. The results were then compared with newly obtained experimental results, validating the model.

1 Introduction

Thermoset plastics are widely utilized in high-performance applications due to their excellent mechanical strength and chemical resistance, which are attributed to their cross-linked network structures. However, this same structural stability poses significant challenges for recycling and environmental sustainability. Unlike thermoplastics, thermosets cannot be remelted or reshaped after curing, making their end-of-life disposal difficult and often reliant on landfilling or incineration. To address this issue, various recycling strategies have been proposed, including mechanical grinding, pyrolysis, and chemical degradation. Among these, chemical recycling via controlled degradation has emerged as a promising approach, especially for thermoset resins containing degradable functional groups such as esters or anhydrides. When such polymers are exposed to water or nucleophilic agents, hydrolytic degradation can occur through cleavage of the labile bonds, resulting in molecular breakdown and partial solubilization [1], [2].

Chemical degradation methods, especially hydrolysis under alkaline conditions, have emerged as promising routes to address this challenge. Previous studies reported significant success using sodium hydroxide (NaOH) for effective hydrolysis of epoxy resins. Recently, glycolysis methods, employing diols like 1,4-butanediol (BDO), have shown potential due to enhanced penetration capability, even though glycolysis reactions were not directly observed in certain cases. Nevertheless, solvent optimization, specifically balancing water and glycol components under alkaline conditions, remains insufficiently explored [3], [4].

In this work, we examined epoxy resin degradation using NaOH solutions mixed with varying volumetric ratios of water and 1,4-butanediol. We hypothesize that while BDO itself might not significantly contribute to glycolysis, its presence may substantially impact hydrolysis reactions by modifying the solution's physicochemical properties, including viscosity and ionic mobility. To quantify this, a modified shrinking-core model was applied, providing kinetic insight into the degradation behavior of epoxy resin under optimized conditions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

All chemicals were used as received. A degradable thermoset epoxy system was prepared using KER9100 epoxy resin and KCA9110 hardener, both supplied by KUMHO P&B Chemicals (Korea).

The solvent employed for glycolysis was 1,4-Butanediol (CAS No. 110-63-4, liquid), while sodium hydroxide (NaOH) in bead form (CAS No. 1310-73-2) was used as the alkaline catalyst for hydrolysis.

2.2 Solvent miscibility

In the first stage, the objective was to determine the solvent ratios at which no phase separation occurs between water and 1,4-Butanediol under alkaline conditions. A 2 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution was prepared by dissolving 4.8 g of NaOH in varying amounts of distilled water. Seven different volumetric ratios were tested: 10:0, 9:1, 8:2, 6:4, 5:5, 3:7, and 2:8, each with a total volume of 60 mL. After adding 1,4-Butanediol to the NaOH aqueous phase, the mixtures were heated to 100°C and stirred at 510 RPM for 2 hours. Visual observations were recorded every 30 minutes to identify phase separation, color change, or precipitation. These observations were used to determine the suitable mixing ratios for subsequent degradation studies.

2.3 Degradation of epoxy resin

Figure 1 Experimental setup for chemical degradation of epoxy resin specimens using varying ratios of water and 1,4-butanediol (BDO) under alkaline conditions.

In the second stage, chemically decomposable cured epoxy resin specimens were cut into uniform shapes. Degradation solutions were prepared by mixing 1.5 L of the 2 M NaOH solution with 1,4-Butanediol at various miscible ratios. Epoxy specimens were enclosed in polyethylene mesh pouches and fixed with Teflon plastic holders. The samples were then immersed into the degradation media inside a three-neck round-bottom flask equipped with a reflux condenser and magnetic stirring system, maintaining both temperature and homogeneity throughout the reaction. Degradation experiments were conducted for 3, 4, and 5 hours, after which the samples were retrieved, washed, dried, and reweighed to assess the mass loss.

3 Modified shrinking-core model

To describe the degradation behavior of epoxy specimens, a modified shrinking-core model was applied, in which the cross-sectional area remains constant and only thickness (height) decreases over time. The decomposition reaction rate is defined as:

$$V = kSC_A \quad (1)$$

Where V is the reaction rate (g/s), k is the rate constant per unit surface area ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), S is the reactive surface area (cm^2), and C_a is the concentration of active species (mol/L). Assuming a square plate with constant surface area ($a \times a$) and height $h(t)$ that decreases over time, the volume of the specimen is expressed as:

$$V = -dm/dt = -d(\rho a^2 h)/dt \quad (2)$$

The degree of degradation and the reactive surface area of the specimen can be defined as:

$$X = 1 - (m / m_0) = 1 - (h / h_0) \quad (3)$$

$$S = 4a \cdot h + 2a^2 = 2a(2h + a) = 2a[2h_0(1 - X) + a] \quad (4)$$

Rearranged into a first-order differential equation and solving this differential equation yields the closed-form solution for the degradation behavior over time:

$$X(t) = 1 + (a / 4h_0)(1 + a / 4h_0)exp(-4kC_A t / (a\rho)) \quad (5)$$

This model describes degradation behavior under the assumption that volume loss occurs only through thickness reduction while surface area remains constant. The model was validated against experimental data, and the rate constant k was estimated for each condition by nonlinear curve fitting of the degradation curves.

4 Results and discussion

Figure 2 Visual comparison of epoxy resin degradation as a function of solvent composition (H₂O:BDO ratios) and reaction duration (1–5 hours).

Figure 2 displays the epoxy resin samples degraded under various solvent ratios (H₂O:BDO) and reaction times (1-5 hours). At initial stages (1-2 hours), samples retained structural integrity. However, increasing reaction time clearly resulted in significant thinning and transparency, indicative of ongoing degradation. Specifically, samples treated with the intermediate solvent ratio (6:4, H₂O:BDO) showed rapid and extensive degradation after just 3 hours, becoming visibly thinner and more transparent. In contrast, at higher or lower BDO ratios, the degradation was noticeably slower, consistent with the kinetic analysis discussed later.

Figure 3 Experimental results of epoxy resin degradation as a function of solvent composition (H₂O:BDO ratios) and reaction duration (1–5 hours).

The relationship between solvent composition and degradation efficiency revealed a distinct optimum around the 6:4 (H₂O:BDO) ratio. Initially, increasing BDO content enhanced the degradation significantly. However, exceeding this optimal concentration resulted in reduced degradation rates. This behavior is attributed primarily to changes in ionization and catalytic activity within the solvent .

NaOH ionization predominantly occurs in water, producing hydroxide ions (OH⁻), essential for epoxy hydrolysis. As the BDO fraction increases, the overall ionization degree of NaOH decreases due to reduced water content. Despite the reduced ionization at lower water ratios, the initial addition of BDO (up to 40%) significantly enhances solution penetration and hydroxide ion diffusion into the epoxy structure. This synergistic effect considerably increases degradation efficiency initially. However, beyond the critical ratio, the decreased ionization severely restricts hydroxide ion availability, reducing overall degradation efficiency.

Figure 4 Gaussian fitting of degradation rate constant (*k*) as a function of solvent composition, identifying the optimal ratio (H₂O:BDO = 6:4).

Experimental degradation rate constants (k) fitted using Gaussian equations (Figure 3) yielded clear optimal solvent ratio insights. The fitting equation is:

$$k(x) = A \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (6)$$

The Gaussian fit gave parameter $A = 8.09 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m/s}$, $\mu = 0.41$, and $\sigma = 0.27$, identifying 0.4 (H₂O:BDO = 6:4) as the optimal solvent ratio. This validates visual and physical observations, demonstrating that BDO enhances hydroxide ion penetration until reaching a critical concentration that negatively affects ionization and reactivity.

Under alkaline conditions, the epoxy resin primarily degrades through hydrolysis, catalyzed by hydroxide ions (OH⁻). Despite initially hypothesizing potential glycolysis contributions by BDO, direct glycolysis reactions were not significantly evident from the observed data. Nevertheless, the presence of BDO significantly enhanced hydrolysis efficiency, attributed to increased hydroxide ion penetration facilitated by altered solvent physicochemical properties.

5 Conclusions

This study successfully demonstrated enhanced epoxy resin degradation under optimized alkaline hydrolysis conditions by controlling solvent ratios of water and 1,4-butanediol. Gaussian fitting provided clear quantitative identification of the optimal solvent composition, supported by visual observations and kinetic analysis via the modified shrinking-core model. Although glycolysis reactions were negligible, BDO significantly improved hydrolysis efficiency through increased hydroxide ion penetration up to a certain critical concentration, beyond which efficiency declined due to reduced ionization. These insights advance epoxy resin recycling strategies, presenting a promising route for environmentally sustainable management of thermosetting polymers.

6 REFERENCES

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